

Multimodal fusion of inertial sensors and single RGB camera data for 3D human pose estimation based on a hybrid LSTM-Random forest fusion network

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ABSTRACT

Over the last decades, the capturing and monitoring of human motions and poses have found increasing interest, with the recent advancements in interconnected sensors and computer vision applications. By effectively fusing data from inertial sensors and visual cues, the limitations that each type of data introduces can be overcome leading to highly accurate human pose estimation. However, in such applications, a complex setup with many multiview cameras and inertial sensors is required for the systems to perform effectively. This work proposes a multimodal fusion system based on a single RGB camera and six inertial sensors for effective human pose estimation. For the unimodal data analysis, two state-of-the-art methods have been adopted; namely the Transformer Inertial Poser network for the inertial sensor data analysis and the MediaPipe's 3D Pose Landmarker for the analysis of the camera data. 3D joint coordinate results from both unimodal analysis methods are fused in a decision-level fusion approach using a hybrid model architecture combining a deep learning network and a machine learning regression model. Two different deep learning network architectures were tested; a fully connected network architecture and a Long Short-Term Memory based network architecture, followed by a Random Forest regression model as the last layer of our hybrid model. Results on the TotalCapture dataset reveal that our method outperforms other state-of-the-art systems, reducing the mean per joint position error by 13.9 mm, while using a simpler data acquisition setup with only a single RGB camera and six inertial sensors.

1. Introduction

The capturing and monitoring of human motions are of increasing interest in a variety of applications, including among others Virtual Reality (VR) [1], Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) [2], entertainment [3] and healthcare [4]. The recent advantages in computer vision and inertial sensing allow for effective human pose estimation in more natural environments, getting released from setup constraints and relieving the user of encumbrances from specialized equipment that incommode the free movements.

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Vision-based solutions attempt to retrieve 3D human pose estimation from 2D images, achieving high levels of accuracy results while not having rigorous setup requirements [5]. Nevertheless, their performance is highly influenced by occlusions and viewing range and angles. On the other hand, inertial sensing can overcome such issues but suffers from sensor drift and performs better in capturing bone orientations rather than joint positions [6]. Thus, the combination of the two modalities can effectively overcome the abovementioned issues while ensuring high levels of accuracy in real-time human pose estimation. Various machine learning, deep learning or optimization approaches have been proposed in the literature for visual-inertial sensing fusion in the application of 3D human pose estimation [7]. However, in these approaches, high numbers of sensors and cameras are required in order for the proposed systems to perform effectively.

In this work, a multimodal system for human pose estimation based on inertial sensors and visual cues is proposed. For our work, we considered data only from one camera for the visual data analysis and six inertial wearables for the sensor data analysis. The unimodal analysis was based on two state-of-the-art solutions; the MediaPipe's 3D Pose Landmarker [8] for the visual data analysis and the Transformer Inertial Poser (TIP) model [9] for the sensor data analysis. The outputs of the two unimodal modules are fused in a decision level fusion manner using a novel hybrid network architecture combining a deep learning network with a machine learning algorithm. Two different deep learning architectures are proposed; a fully connected dense network and a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network, in combination with a Random Forest regression algorithm as the last layer of the hybrid fusion network for the machine learning model.

The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- we propose a novel hybrid network architecture, combining deep learning networks with a machine learning algorithm. This hybrid network is used for decision-level fusion of 3D human pose estimation results from inertial and visual data analysis for effective multimodal 3D human pose estimation
- we prove the superiority of the proposed hybrid architecture over simple deep learning models by providing comparative results of the mean per joint position error on the publicly available TotalCapture multimodal dataset
- we achieve beyond state-of-the-art results using the TotalCapture dataset, reducing the mean per joint position error by 13.9 mm compared to other state-of-the-art proposed solutions
- we showcase that a simple setup of only 6 inertial sensors and a single RGB camera is as effective as or even better than more complex setups having up to 13 inertial sensors and a set of 8 RGB cameras for multiview visual inputs

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: in Section 2 the current state-of-the-art in the field of 3D pose estimation is presented, categorized into vision-based solutions, sensor-based methods and multimodal fusion approaches. In Section 3, the methods for the multimodal fusion pipeline for 3D human pose estimation based on visual and inertial sensing in this work are presented in detail followed by quantitative, qualitative and comparable results with other state-of-the-art proposed solutions in Section 4. Finally, in Section 5, a final conclusion of the current work is presented along with future steps.

2. Related work

There are three main approaches for the application of 3D human pose estimation, namely visual-based, wearable-based and multimodal fusion-based pose estimation.

2.1. Visual-based pose estimation

In recent years, a great focus has been given to the direction of 3D human body estimation from RGB input, exploiting the recent advancements in computer vision and deep learning techniques. The proposed methods hold great promise for the development of applications in virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), motion analysis, and human-computer interaction. Both skeleton-only and 3D human mesh recovery methods have been proposed [10]. Within the context of this work, discussion about skeleton-only methods that take as input single-view images or videos is made.

Cai et al. [11] leveraged spatial-temporal relationships and constraints, including bone-length and left-right symmetry constraints, to enhance the performance of 3D human pose estimation across consecutive frames. Pavlo et al. [12] introduced a temporal convolution network designed to estimate 3D pose based on 2D keypoints from 2D sequences. Nevertheless, their methodology assumes that prediction errors are temporally non-continuous and independent, a premise that may not remain valid when occlusions are present [13]. Recently, BlazePose GHUM 3D, a convolutional neural network [14] designed for the human body's 3D pose estimation for real-world applications, was developed by Google. Its architecture comprises three major parts: a body pose estimation network, a depth estimation network, and post-processing. This implementation was integrated into Google's MediaPipe 3D body landmark detector [8].

2.2. Wearable-based pose estimation

Compared to visual-based approaches, wearable-based pose estimation solutions are robust to occlusion (i.e., have no location-based restrictions) and poor lighting. One of the very first important works in this field is the Sparse Inertial Poser (SIP) [15], which optimizes the sequence of poses to match the recorded signals for offline joint angle reconstruction exploiting a configuration of six IMUs, without using human motion prior. On the other hand, Deep Inertial Poser (DIP) [16] introduced the use of prior knowledge, where a bi-directional Recurrent Neural Network (bi-RNN) architecture is trained using an extensive synthesized dataset; namely

the AMASS motion dataset [17], to reconstruct joint angles based on a history of IMU measurements. DIP architecture is considered to run online with a small latency, despite the fact that it relies on a non-efficient neural network family (i.e., bi-RNNs). This is accomplished by using as input only a small window size. Similarly, TransPose [18] is based on several RNNs and bi-RNNs to predict the full pose, along with accurately estimating the root motion by fusing predictions of foot velocities, root velocities and contact probabilities rather than directly predicting root motion.

The same group of researchers, extended DIP by introducing Physics Inertial Poser (PIP) [19], which adds a physics layer to refine the joint orientations and root motion predictions. The intuition is that the whole-body pose should be compliant with the physics of the rigid body dynamics of the used Skinned Multi-Person Linear (SMPL) model [20], where the external forces can result from contact between the feet and the ground (i.e., in case they are predicted to actually be in contact). Another approach for root motion translation estimations is provided by TIP [9]; this model predicts stationary boundary points on feet, hands and pelvis and applies a geometric correction on the whole-body motion by taking the assumption that the predicted stationary points need to be static. PIP and TIP are considered to be state-of-the-art when it comes to results in terms of both joint orientations (mean absolute joint errors 8–15 degrees) and significantly reduce root drift error compared to TransPose while having small enough latency (<100 ms) to assume they can run online.

2.3. Multimodal fusion-based pose estimation

Different methods have been reported in the literature for multimodal fusion of visual and inertial sensors for the cause of full-body human pose estimation. These methods are either based on deep learning networks [21], filter methods [22] or deterministic and optimization approaches [23,24]. In the work of Lu et al. [25] the authors proposed a multimodal system for pose estimation of bike riders based on a monocular camera and wearable gyroscopes. Their fusion scheme is based on an extended Kalman Filter for estimating whole-body pose while also introducing human anatomy constraints and the physical rider-bike interaction. The authors in [26] proposed a fusion scheme based on a deep learning approach, more specifically a dense Neural Network (NN). By introducing such an architecture as the last step of their analysis, they were able to effectively fuse the unimodal pose estimation results from the visual and inertial sensors. Similarly, in their follow-up work [27], they replaced this dense neural network architecture with an LSTM-based network, which is more suitable for such applications as an RNN. Von Marcard [24] associated 2D pose estimations from images with IMU-based poses by introducing a graph optimization component, transitioning from the 2D to the 3D space. In [28] a kinematic solution is proposed, based on pose parameterization. They introduced a pose estimation cost function to be optimized based on multiple 2D keypoints position detections from camera inputs, and joint orientation and acceleration terms derived from the IMUs. They also introduced a floor penetration term, ensuring no joints will be predicted below the floor level, as well as a principal component analysis term to constrain all degrees of freedom since not all predicted joints are observed in the IMU input.

Our work goes beyond other state-of-the-art solutions based on decision-level fusion by introducing a novel hybrid network architecture, combining deep learning networks with a machine learning algorithm. This novel architecture aims at exploiting the benefits from both methods in a complementary way, in order to improve the performance of multimodal 3D human pose estimation.

3. Methods

Our proposed approach is based on two different unimodal analysis components, the computer vision-based module and the wearable-based module. Both modules are used to monitor 3D joint coordinates based on camera and inertial sensors respectively. In the final stage of our solution, a multimodal fusion component is designed in order to effectively combine the outputs of the aforementioned modules for the final 3D human pose estimation. The whole pipeline of our work can be seen in Fig. 1.

3.1. Computer vision-based solution

Concerning the computer vision-based solution, MediaPipe's 3D Pose Landmarker [8] was used to estimate the subject's 3D body landmarks using RGB input video. The MediaPipe algorithm produces 33 3D-space points that represent body landmarks, as seen in Fig. 2A. These landmarks can be either normalized coordinates or world coordinates. More specifically, the 'x' and 'y' normalized landmark coordinates take values in [0.0, 1.0] by the video frame width ('x') and height ('y'). The 'z' coordinates, which represent the landmark's depth, are measured from the midpoint of the hips, which is the origin point. Therefore, the landmark is closer to the camera the smaller the value. Additionally, the 'visibility' of every body landmark is provided; this can be expressed as a value between 0.0 and 1.0 and represents the probability that the landmark will be visible, meaning it will be present and not obscured, in the processed video frame. The 3D ground-truth landmarks used to train the BlazePose landmark tracker were generated using a statistical 3D human body model named GHUM [29]. There are 3 BlazePose model versions (Heavy, Full, Lite) each one with a different capacity, that provide various levels of tradeoff between accuracy and on-device inference speed. As far as the landmarks tracker model (BlazePose GHUM 3D), the Lite version has 1.3M Params, the Full has 3.1M Params and the Heavy has 13.7M Params. In Fig. 3 you can see a video frame example that comes from the TotalCapture dataset along with the Mediapipe's landmarks.

In our experiments, the 33 MediaPipe world body landmarks were extracted for all five subjects and all actions performed in the TotalCapture videos from camera number 1 (front face camera). To achieve higher estimation accuracy, the Heavy version of the MediaPipe model was employed. When a subject is entirely absent from a video frame, the computer vision-based method cannot

Fig. 1. The pipeline of the proposed multimodal fusion 3D pose estimation.

Fig. 2. Comparison of MediaPipe's 3D body landmarks positions and SMPL model pose 3D joint positions. A: The 33 3D body landmarks produced by the MediaPipe pose landmark detector. B: The 20 3D body landmarks of the SMPL model.

detect any body landmarks and yields no output. However, when even some parts of the body are visible, the algorithm provides estimations for all body landmarks.

It is also important to note that the body landmarks generated by MediaPipe's algorithm do not precisely match those of the SMPL model poses [20], that are used for the rest of the paper, as can be seen in Fig. 2. There are 13 common landmarks between the MediaPipe's 3D pose results and the SMPL joints, thus these 13 common joints are used for both the evaluation of the vision-based analysis and as input for the multimodal fusion module.

For the pose estimation process Mediapipe uses BlazePose [14] which is a lightweight convolution neural network (CNN) optimized for on-device, real-time fitness applications. BlazePose's estimation pipeline consists of two stages: a person detector (BlazePose detector) and a landmarks tracker (BlazePose GHUM 3D). The detector outputs a bounding box which is used as input for the tracker. The tracker detects 33 3D body landmarks in both image and world coordinates, the visibility and presence for each landmark and the probability a person is present on a passed bounding box. In total the landmarks tracker outputs 265 parameters ($33 \times 3 \times 2 + 33 \times 2 + 1$). The tracker follows an architecture similar to MobileNetV2 [30]. The 3D world landmarks are in relative coordinates of a metric space with origin in the subject's hips center. The person detector does not run on every frame but only if the landmarks tracker indicates that there is no human present in the last bounding box proposed. The person detector uses a face detector under the hood as it is easier to detect a human face instead of the whole body. However, this face detector predicts additional person specific alignment parameters: the middle point between the person's hips, the size of the circle circumscribing the

Fig. 3. Example of MediaPipe's body landmark detection using input video from the TotalCapture dataset.

whole person etc. The bounding box that is generated from the detector and used as input in the landmarks tracker is a $256 \times 256 \times 3$ array with aligned human full body part, centered by mid-hip in vertical body pose and rotation distortion of $(-10, 10)$. Channels order: RGB with values in $[0.0, 1.0]$.

3.2. Wearable-based solution

The wearable-based solution makes use of six IMU sensors placed on the user's head, waist and body extremities. The employed model for this test case is TIP [9]. The system integrates a learning based Transformer decoder model [31] and an analytical drift stabilizer. The former estimates the full-body joint angles, their coordinates, the root velocity, and the Stationary Body Points (SBPs) from IMU orientation and acceleration signals, while the latter uses the SBPs during runtime to enhance motion prediction accuracy and minimize drift errors over time.

The training data used in TIP is 12 AMASS subsets for SMPL-H model [20], passed through an IMU synthesis procedure, as described in DIP [16], as they do not contain real IMU data. The main input for TIP is calibrated orientation $R \in \mathbb{R}^{54 \times (M+1)}$ and acceleration $\bar{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{36 \times (M+1)}$ after smoothing filtering or integration, which are obtained from six IMU sensors from the waist, wrists, knees and head locations. The output includes 18 joint angles $q_t \in \mathbb{R}^{108}$ as defined in the SMPL human model (excluding hands, wrists and toes), the root linear velocity $v_t \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and the SBPs $c_t \in \mathbb{R}^{20}$. The window size M is set as 39, while the root orientation is given by the waist IMU.

The Transformer Motion Estimator's (TME) architecture can be characterized as a conditional Transformer decoder [31]. During training, the sequences of IMU readings are fed to the model in parallel to its past M predictions, time shifted by one step. At first, the TME concatenates the input and output data which is then passed through a linear layer. Subsequently, the data are passed to four Transformer blocks, made up of a multi-head attention and feedforward network; each one uses a residual connection with the previous layer followed by a layer normalization operation. Additionally, the TME incorporates a unidirectional Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) layer to summarize output embedding of the Transformer, employing a hyperbolic tangent (tanh) activation function. Finally, the output of the RNN layer undergoes a final linear transformation, producing the TME's output results, namely q_t , v_t , and c_t . Standard loss functions are used for the predicted output data, mean squared error for q_t , v_t and Cartesian elements of c_t , and binary cross-entropy for binary elements of c_t . The current timestep SBP data are then forwarded to the TME input through the history prediction.

After the TME predicts the joint angles, the root linear velocity and the SBPs, these data are then forwarded to the drift stabilizer. A run-time root and joint correction are performed. The predicted SBPs serve as constraints to correct the root velocity v_t , stabilizing the motion in the horizontal plane. For joint angle q_t correction, when a pair of SBPs are active for consecutive frames, a two-bone Inverse Kinematics (IK) [32] technique is used, leveraging the TME's dependency on its own history of predictions and, thus, preserving the distance vector between the two points. The corrected joint angle predictions are forwarded to the history buffer to be used as the input by the TME.

It should be noted that in the current work, we use the minimal version of TIP, where the terrain generation module is omitted. As the TotalCapture dataset used for evaluation does not contain uneven terrains, the module is not necessary and TIP's output is not affected by it, since it is used for visualization purposes.

Fig. 4. The fully connected network architecture used for fusion. The network receives the concatenated results from visual and sensor analysis as input and produces a fused 3D joint coordinate estimation output.

3.3. Multimodal fusion

The complementary nature of the visual and inertial information for pose estimation can be exploited by developing a robust multimodal fusion module, as the final step of our pipeline. The MediaPipe's 3D landmarks position estimations produced from the visual data analysis and the 3D joint coordinates resulted from the wearable sensor-based solution can serve as input to the multimodal fusion component of our pipeline. Our proposed fusion approach is a decision-level fusion scheme, which is responsible for integrating the results from the unimodal components into a final pose estimation result. The module is based on a hybrid architecture combining a deep learning network with a machine learning regressor as the final step of the estimation of 3D joint positions by receiving as input the 20 3D joint coordinates from the sensor analysis and the positions from the 3D coordinates from the 13 common landmarks produced from the MediaPipe's 3D Pose Landmarker as a concatenated vector with length of $20 \cdot 3 + 13 \cdot 3 = 99$.

For the machine learning algorithm, after evaluating different regression models, a Random Forest (RF) regression model was selected. The Random Forest algorithm is based on multiple decision trees, whose individual predictions are aggregated in the final step using an averaging technique. This ensemble nature is able to improve generalization and can help smooth out noise and provide more stable predictions [33].

Regarding the deep learning network two different architectures have been proposed. The first architecture was based on a Fully Connected (FC) network with multiple layers that can integrate the results from both unimodal analyses meaningfully into a final pose prediction. The architecture of this FC network can be seen in Fig. 4.

Apart from the fully connected network architecture, a solution based on an LSTM cell [34] is also proposed. By incorporating such an architecture, the temporal nature of human movement and poses can be exploited. Compared to classic RNNs, the LSTM network architecture can achieve better results in many different applications, including video description [35], speech recognition [36] and language translation [37]. With the introduction of the memory cell and the gate units into the cell structure, the LSTM layer is able to reveal long-term dependencies as well [38].

In our work, an LSTM cell with 176 units and a look back of 5 frames was used as can be seen in Fig. 5. Both the fully connected and the LSTM-based architectures were trained using an Adam optimizer [39] with a learning rate of 10^{-2} . All stages of both models are implemented using TensorFlow.

After the training of the deep learning networks, the last layer was removed and replaced by the RF regression model, as seen in Fig. 6. This hybrid architecture can leverage the diversity of individual machine learning and deep learning methods and complement the strengths of each approach. The deep learning network serves as a feature extraction network exploiting the ability of deep learning networks to learn complex feature representations. The RF algorithm serves as the final 3D joints coordinate predictor, receiving the extracted features from the deep learning network as input, since it is able to reveal non-linear effects of its predictors [33].

Fig. 5. The LSTM-based network architecture used for fusion. The network receives the concatenated results from visual and sensor analysis of 5 frames as input and produces a fused 3D joint coordinate estimation output.

4. Results

In this Section, the results of our proposed method are described and also comparative results between our method and other proposed state-of-the-art solutions are provided.

4.1. Dataset

For the proposed solutions in this paper, all the experiments were performed using the TotalCapture dataset [26] which is a publicly available multimodal dataset for pose estimation with multiple inertial sensors and cameras. The dataset contains fully synchronized data from 13 body-worn XSens IMU sensors [6] on key body parts (head, upper/lower back, upper/lower arms and legs and feet) and 8 calibrated full HD video cameras recording at 60 Hz with high-quality ground truth values derived from Vicon motion capture [40]. Five subjects are included in the dataset performing 3 iterations of 4 different actions; *walking, acting, freestyle and range of motion (ROM)*.

For the evaluation of our new method, we preferred the camera that had the most frames with the subjects present from TotalCapture for the computer-vision module, which is labeled as “camera 1”. As for the wearable-based one, we selected only six IMU, mounted on the subject’s head, lower back, wrists and tibiae. The selection of the sensor locations is based on the relevant research done on the field [9,16,18,19].

4.2. Pose estimation results

All of our experiments were carried out in 3D coordinate space. TIP model was implemented using PyTorch, the MediaPipe’s 3D Pose Landmarker is provided in TFlite format, the LSTM part of fusion was implemented using TensorFlow, while the RF regressor is trained using scikit-learn. The computations of the deployed models for the sensor data analysis and multimodal fusion were performed on a NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4060 Laptop GPU. The MediaPipe’s Pose Landmarker computations were performed on a 13th Gen Intel Core i7-13700HX.

For the evaluation of all components of our pipeline, the mean per joint position error (MPJPE) metric was assessed. The MPJPE computes the mean distance between the predicted joint positions and the ground truth joint positions, as in Eq. (1).

$$MPJPE = \frac{1}{N_{joints}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{N_{joints}} \sqrt{(x_i - \hat{x}_i)^2 + (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 + (z_i - \hat{z}_i)^2} \tag{1}$$

where N_{joints} is the number of joints, x_i, y_i, z_i are the ground truth x, y, z coordinates of the joint i and $\hat{x}_i, \hat{y}_i, \hat{z}_i$ are the predicted x, y, z coordinates for the joint i .

Fig. 6. Hybrid fusion model architecture with A: fully connected network and Random Forest, B: LSTM-based network and Random Forest.

Table 1
Comparative results of different regression models as the last layer of hybrid architecture with LSTM as the DL layer.

Regression model	MPJPE (cm)
Gradient Boosting regressor	10.46
Support Vector Machines regressor	10.43
Decision Tree regressor	4.05
k Nearest Neighbors regressor	3.09
Random Forest	1.21

4.2.1. Regression models study

In order to select the best-performing machine learning model as the last layer of the proposed hybrid architecture, a study on different regression models was performed. The results of the study of different regression models are presented in Table 1. In the presented results, the LSTM network was chosen as the deep learning architecture as it is the one performing better. From the Table it can be seen that the RF regression model outperforms the rest of the regression models achieving an MPJPE of 1.21 cm, thereby being the one selected to serve as the last layer of the proposed hybrid DL-ML architecture.

Table 2
Comparison of the proposed work with other state-of-the-art solutions on the TotalCapture dataset.

Work	Setup	Method	Evaluation split (test set)	MPJPE (cm)
[41]	1 camera & 13 IMUs	Optimize pose estimation with image- and IMU-based constraints	walking 2, acting 3, freestyle 3 all subjects	13.5
[27]	8 cameras & 13 IMUs	CNN for 3D pose estimation from 3D poses from multiple images, IMU kinematic solve and LSTM and dense layers for fusion	walking 2, acting 3, freestyle 3 all subjects	4.26
[21]	8 cameras & 13 IMUs	CNN for 3D pose estimation from visual data, refinement with network for IMUs, deep fusion with softmax layer	not stated	2.89
[28]	8 cameras & 13 IMUs	Kinematic solution based on pose parameterization, pose estimation cost function optimization and multiple 2D keypoints position detection	freestyle 1 subjects 2, 3, 5 freestyle 3 subjects 1, 3, 4 rom 3 subject 2 acting 3 subject 5	2.61
[24]	1 camera & 13 IMUs	Association of 2D pose detection of each image with IMU-based poses with graph optimization	walking 2, acting 3, freestyle 3 all subjects	2.6
Ours	1 camera & 6 IMUs	Fusion of TIP and MediaPipe's results with LSTM-RF hybrid network	Leave-one-subject-out cross-validation	1.21

Table 3
Ablation study results on the input data and on the hybrid ML-DL architecture.

Method	MPJPE (cm)
Unimodal analysis results	
Visual sensors - MediaPipe	15.21
Inertial sensors - TIP	5.48
Results of proposed architecture on unimodal input	
Input - Inertial sensor only	2.69
Multimodal analysis results - deep learning networks	
FC network	2.72
LSTM network	1.49
Multimodal analysis results - hybrid networks	
FC-RF hybrid network	1.41
LSTM-RF hybrid network	1.21

4.2.2. Comparative analysis

Comparative results against other state-of-the-art solutions on the TotalCapture dataset are depicted in Table 2. From the Table, it can be seen that our work outperforms other state-of-the-art solutions by reducing the mean per joint position error by 13.9 mm while also having the simplest setup by only using 1 camera and 6 IMU sensors. We also trained our fusion model using leave-one-subject-out cross-validation, meaning the test subject is not known to the model, ensuring the model's generalization and robustness.

4.2.3. Ablation study

In this section, an ablation study is performed to evaluate the performance of the proposed architecture on unimodal input and to study the effects of adding the RF regression model as the last layer of our fusion module. The MPJPE results of this analysis can be seen in Table 3. Additionally, a comparative analysis is presented between the unimodal analysis results and the fusion module results. Also in Fig. 7, we present per activity and per subject results for all unimodal and fusion subcomponents, showcasing the robustness of LSTM-RF architecture, since it outperforms the rest models in all validation sets and activities.

The role of the multimodal fusion module: For the computer vision-based 3D pose estimation, the MPJPE metric was assessed exclusively including frames where the subject was fully visible, resulting in an MPJPE of 15.21 cm. Since only a single camera data was used for the computer vision-based 3D pose estimation algorithm, the transition from the 2D images to the 3D landmark

Fig. 7. Barplots of MPJPE of all unimodal and multimodal subcomponents (A) per activity and (B) per subject.

coordinates leads to increased errors in the computation of the depth of the joint positions, which is reflected in the MPJPE results. It is worth noting that frames without subjects present were excluded only for the evaluation of the computer vision-based 3D pose estimation module, since frames without subjects present would produce significant errors in the results leading in not fair comparisons with the rest of the reported results.

By evaluating the TIP model on the IMU dataset provided by TotalCapture, the MPJPE result was 5.48 cm. Additionally, as raw data output from the TIP model itself, we obtain the predicted 18 joint angles, the root linear velocity and the SBPs. Lastly, visualization processing provides us with the predicted joint positions. These joint positions were used as the IMU input to the multimodal fusion component of our pipeline.

In order to evaluate whether the deeper architecture proposed or the fusion of both visual and sensor modalities is responsible for the improved performance, an ablation study on the input of our hybrid LSTM-RF architecture was performed. In Table 3 the results of the MPJPE of the hybrid LSTM-RF architecture when using only the TIP results as input indicate an improvement in the performance, dropping MPJPE from 5.48 cm to 2.69 cm. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that since the TIP model has not been fine-tuned on the TotalCapture dataset, the deeper architecture serves as a fine-tuning layer. The improved performance is not close enough to the results of our proposed fusion framework, where both results from TIP and MediaPipe are concatenated as inputs. The fusion of the two modalities allows for the exchange of information between them, leading to improved performance.

It is worth noting that an ablation study using only MediaPipe's results as input is not feasible, due to MediaPipe producing hips-based results, meaning that the results do not capture movement in space. Since the goal of the proposed methodology is to produce results in a global coordinate system that captures movements in space, as also are the ground truth values of the TotalCapture dataset, it is not fair to use only MediaPipe's results as input to the added architecture and compare their performance with the rest of the results.

The exploitation of both modalities by the fusion module, improves the performance of the system in terms of MPJPE, in both the simple deep learning architecture and in the hybrid fusion architecture. The complementary nature of the visual and inertial sensors for human pose estimation is revealed by introducing a multimodal fusion module. In both the simple deep learning and hybrid fusion architecture, the LSTM-based approach performs better, since it can perceive the temporal nature of human movements and poses.

The role of the RF regression model layer: In both the cases of the FC and the LSTM network architectures, the introduction of an RF regression model as the last prediction layer improves the performance of the model in terms of the MPJPE. Our hybrid approach benefits from the complex feature representation capabilities of the deep learning models and the means of the RF model to reveal non-linear relations of its predictors' outputs.

4.2.4. Qualitative results

Lastly, we also present qualitative results of our LSTM-RF hybrid fusion architecture for subject 2 of the TotalCapture dataset. In Fig. 8 all different actions of the TotalCapture dataset are presented against the ground truth values. In most cases, it can be seen that our method follows the ground truth poses with very high accuracy. Nevertheless, there are cases where there are errors in the predictions of our method. In more detail, there are two different types of errors. The first type of error is the incorrect predictions of poses, which is noted in Fig. 8 with grey boxes. In these example cases, it can be seen that our method predicts different poses than those of the ground truth poses. The second type of error is the dislocation of the whole predicted pose as seen in Fig. 8 noted in the green box. In this example, the predicted body pose is dislocated as the full body pose is predicted to be further to the right compared to the ground truth pose.

Fig. 8. Example results of the LSTM-based fusion network over the ground truth values of the TotalCapture dataset.

Table 4
Details on the efficiency of the models used in the proposed multimodal fusion pipeline.

Model	Device	Prec.	Size	Params	Time	Ops
TIP	GPU	FP32	14.7 Mb	3.68 m	5.535 ms	130.78k
MediaPipe	CPU	FP16	27.06 Mb	13.75 m	63.40 ms	3,854k
LSTM	GPU	FP32	1.7 Mb	0.415 m	18.01 ms	1,322k
RF	CPU	FP32	6.87 Mb	n/a	0.182 ms	572.8k

4.2.5. Efficiency

In the current section, we provide details on the efficiency of the proposed multimodal fusion framework. In particular, in Table 4 we break down the computational properties of each model used, reporting the device used for the deployment.

As it is shown, the numerical precision of the all the models is equal to floating-point format occupying 32bits (FP32), with the exception of MediaPipe’s 3D Pose Landmarker which is provided in a flite FP16 format. It is worth mentioning that, event though this model is the only one compressed, due to the fact it has high computational complexity of 3.854 million operations and since it runs on CPU (Intel Core i7-13700HX), it is significantly slower than TIP and LSTM that were deployed on a GPU (NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4060). Finally, the proposed LSTM-RF hybrid network is considered to have medium complexity (i.e., 1894,8k operations in total) and a reasonable response time (18.192 ms).

5. Conclusions

In the current work, we proposed a solution for multimodal pose estimation based on visual and inertial sensor fusion in a decision-level manner. The unimodal analysis is based on current state-of-the-art methods; the IMU sensor analysis is based on the TIP model while the visual data analysis is based on the MediaPipe’s 3D Pose Landmarker. Results from the unimodal analysis models are fused in a decision-level manner by using a hybrid machine learning and deep learning approach. Two different deep learning networks were designed; one fully connected network and one LSTM-based network. In both network architectures, the final layer was replaced with a Random Forest machine learning algorithm, forming a hybrid network architecture that exploits complementary strengths from both deep learning and machine learning models. All the experiments were conducted on the publicly available TotalCapture dataset, which contains 8 fully synchronized multiview videos and 13 body-worn IMU sensors. Results reveal that our method overcomes other state-of-the-art solutions by achieving a mean per joint position error metric of 1.21 cm, which is 13.9 mm lower than state-of-the-art solutions, while also having a simpler setup than other methods by only using a single camera and 6 IMU sensors.

Our solution can be expanded to other datasets containing both camera and IMU (orientation, acceleration) data, granted that they are located in the body segments of interest as previously mentioned. The required hardware includes a camera for the computer-vision based module and six IMU for the wearable-based. In the evaluation of our method, both the camera and the IMU that were used from TotalCapture provided recordings with a frame rate of 60 FPS. However, the proposed fusion pipeline depends on the selected time window and not the sampling rates.

A limitation of our work stands on the latency of the whole framework, which prevents it from being considered as a real-time pose estimation application. Specifically, MediaPipe's Pose Landmarker with model complexity 2 (Heavy version) runs at 63.4 ms for 1 prediction (measured using an Intel Core i7-13700HX), while the TIP and the hybrid LSTM-RF multimodal fusion model run at 5.535 ms and at 18.01 ms respectively, using an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4060 GPU. Since in our framework, the unimodal analysis models run in parallel before the multimodal fusion module, the total latency of a single prediction is 81.41 ms (i.e., 12.28 fps). In applications like VR, where extremely fast response times are critical, such a runtime might not be fast enough to provide a seamless user experience.

As a next step for sensor analysis, the examination of calibration methods that can adapt to changes in the sensor characteristics over time is advised, in order to address errors in estimation. In addition, investigating the application of compression techniques (e.g., quantization or knowledge distillation) to the examined model could also prove valuable. The objective is to reduce the memory footprint and enhance the inference speed for deployment on edge devices. As far as the computer vision-based 3D pose estimation solution is concerned, MediaPipe's pose estimation algorithm does not provide bones' rotation information, while depth information is in some cases inaccurate, particularly when the individual raises their hands over their head. Consequently, our future research will concentrate on also obtaining bones' rotation information by exploiting the visual input, as well as correcting depth inaccuracies using machine learning techniques, providing enhanced data for the final fusion step. Regarding the proposed fusion scheme, optimization or filtering methods, like Kalman filters, can be considered in order to minimize the predicted joint position uncertainties and abrupt false movements. Also as a next step, the joint orientation and angle should be considered as target values as well, in order for a more robust human pose estimation process.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vasileios-Rafail Xefteris: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Amalia Contiero Syropoulou:** Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Theodora Pistola:** Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Panagiotis Kasnesis:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Ilias Poullos:** Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation. **Athina Tsanousa:** Writing – review & editing. **Spyridon Symeonidis:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Sotiris Diplaris:** Project administration. **Kostas Goulianas:** Supervision. **Periklis Chatzimisios:** Supervision. **Stefanos Vrochidis:** Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data used are from a publicly available dataset. The code developed is not made available.

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